

PERCEPTIONS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND DIGITAL LITERACY SKILLS; A SURVEY OF UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS, UNIVERSITY OF BALOCHISTAN, QUETTA

Muhammad Saleem Kurdzada^{*1}, Abdullah Jan², Nasir Khan³, Muhammad Anwar⁴

^{*1}Librarian; Govt: Boys Postgraduate College Sibi, Balochistan

²Librarian, government boys degree college dera Allah yar

³Librarian, Government Shaeed Mir Auranzaib Langau Boys Inter College Khaliqabad, Kalat.

⁴Assistant Professor, department of Library and information science, University of Balochistan Quetta

¹saleem.6546@gmail.com, ²abdullahchamp143@gmail.com, ³nasirkhanbaloch77@gmail.com

DOI:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17358326>

Keywords

Artificial Intelligence, Digital Literacy, Undergraduate Students, Higher Education, Balochistan, Perceptions

Article History

Received: 24 August 2025

Accepted: 02 October 2025

Published: 15 October 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Muhammad Saleem

Kurdzada

Abstract

Purpose: This study seeks to understand how undergraduate students at the University of Balochistan, Quetta, perceive and understand artificial intelligence (AI) and digital literacy skills. It also attempts to evaluate the association between the students' understanding of AI and their digital literacy skills to advocate for the inclusion of both in higher education.

Design/Methodology/Approach: A quantitative research design strategy was adopted. A questionnaire was administered to 250 undergraduate students, of which 230 valid responses were obtained through online and face-to-face methods. The primary research instrument consisted of AI perceptions, AI usage, and digital literacy competence Likert-scale and close-ended questions. The research employed frequency and percent distribution using Microsoft Excel.

Findings: The results showed that the students had some familiarity with AI and saw it as an educational game changer; however, the students had gaps with formal training in digital literacy. Regarding digital literacy, 58% of respondents stated that they were confident in their online information evaluative skills, and 52% stated that digital literacy was of utmost importance for success. Issues that respondents pointed out were lack of institutional support, inadequate training, and lack of digital access.

Practical implications: Implementing comprehensive digital literacy and AI awareness training into university programs may elevate students' preparedness for an AI-integrated world. This involves tailored training focused on filling digital gaps and fostering critical thinking towards technology and its responsible use.

Originality/Value: This study adds to the scarce empirical literature concerning the perception of AI within digital literacy and the educational landscape of higher education in Pakistan, specifically the region of Balochistan. This will inform digital education initiatives to keep in line with global technological changes.

INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI)

When one hears the word artificial intelligence (AI), they frequently picture talking computers or robots. In computer science, artificial intelligence is a field that focuses on machine learning, information interpretation, vision, including character recognition, picture analysis, 3D perception, and eye function modeling. It also includes speech recognition, speech production, natural language processing, understanding and using natural language, and expert systems, which is gaining more and more attention. (McGraw-Hill Encyclopedia of Science and Technology (2007), Additionally, artificial intelligence refers to the development and programming of computers to carry out tasks requiring human intellect, such as language translation, speech recognition, visual perception, decision-making, communicating, and emotional processing (Irizarry-Nones, Palepu, & Wallace, 2017).

The science and engineering of building intelligent devices, particularly clever computer programmes, is known as artificial intelligence (AI), according to McCarthy (2007). The aim of AI is to understand the nature of intelligence and build computer systems that can react and act intelligently. The first wave of artificial intelligence has already been ushered in by basic web search, which suggests relevant results based on user searches. Intelligence is the ability to understand, acquire knowledge and skills, and apply them when necessary. The thought of building computers or other technologies with human-like perception, learning, reasoning, and behaviour excites a lot of people. From birth, humans are able to see, reason, and act; over time, for a variety of reasons, this ability develops and becomes better. The Intelligence Quotient (IQ) measures human intelligence and is ascertained by the administration of a battery of aptitude tests covering a wide range of intellectual domains. The creation of sentient machines that see, think, and behave like humans is also at the heart of artificial intelligence (AI).

When a computer or other machine demonstrates intelligence, it implies that it can do a specific job in the face of uncertainty, keep an eye on its environment, and adjust its behaviour depending on what it believes to be required for intelligence. According to the McGraw-Hill Encyclopaedia of Science and Technology (2007), machine intelligence is an anthropomorphism as intelligence is defined as the criteria by which an action

would look clever if carried out by a human. Machines are intelligent, according to Ex Libris (2019), since they are built to efficiently detect and process patterns on far bigger sizes than humans. These gadgets have intelligence, which not only enables learning but also allows them to improve with continued usage. Explicit programming is not required for this improvement to occur. The rapid advancement of artificial intelligence (AI) and the expanding use of digital technology (DT) in a variety of industries have had a profound impact on modern civilization. Once confined to science fiction, artificial intelligence (AI) is becoming a ubiquitous force pushing innovation in industries including healthcare, finance, education, and transportation. Comprehending public perception and the digital skills required to navigate this environment grow more crucial as AI technologies develop. Given that educational settings shape the next generation of professionals and leaders, this is particularly important (Russell, S., & Norvig, P. 2020).

Artificial intelligence focuses on three main areas: perception, logic, and action. Reasoning is a critical component in intelligence gathering. Computers are made to think out the best course of action before acting on it using internal processes or programming logic/algorithms. As stated in the Science and Technology McGraw-Hill Encyclopaedia (2007), Additional meanings of AI include: building mind-capable machines (Haugeland, 1985); studying mental functions using computational models (Charniak & McDermott, 1985); explaining and simulating intelligent behavior using computational processes (Schalkoff, 1990); and applying science and engineering to the creation of intelligent machines and computer programs (John McCarthy). Artificial Intelligence covers both machine representations of information and the concepts and methods of symbolic judgements. Its objective is to perform cognitive functions such as reasoning, learning new abilities, and adapting to unfamiliar situations and problems (Nilson, 1998 cited in Shohana, 2016). In short, artificial intelligence (AI) is the process of giving computers or other machines intelligence akin to that of people so they can solve complex problems in a manner that is comparable to that of humans.

The rapid advancement of artificial intelligence (AI) and the expanding use of digital technology (DT) in a variety of industries have had a profound impact on modern civilization. Once confined to science fiction, artificial intelligence (AI) is becoming a ubiquitous force pushing

innovation in industries including healthcare, finance, education, and transportation. Comprehending public perception and the digital skills required to navigate this world grow more crucial as AI

technologies develop. Given that educational settings shape the next generation of professionals and leaders, this is particularly important (Russell, S., & Norvig, P. 2020).

Information Literacy (IL);

Finding and comprehending information is crucial in today's digital environment. Information literacy can help with that! It all comes down to reading, finding, and using knowledge wisely. Being a decent citizen, going to school, and working all benefit from this talent. It assists us in sifting through a plethora of data, determining what is reliable, and applying that data to make informed decisions. Critical thinking, moral behaviour, and sharing our unquestionably acquired knowledge are the cornerstones of information literacy. The ability to successfully comprehend, locate, assess, and apply knowledge was defined by the Association for College and Research Libraries (ACRL, 2000). This skill set is essential for academic research, professional development, and informed citizenship because it allows people to traverse vast volumes of data, recognise trustworthy sources, and use knowledge to make well-informed judgements. Information literacy is a methodical approach to information processing that includes critical thinking, ethical reasoning, and skillful knowledge sharing.

On the other hand, media literacy is defined by Livingstone et al. (2008) as the capacity to understand and evaluate media content as a means of expression and communication. Media literacy encompasses the following skills: producing media content ethically, understanding the role of media in society, and critically evaluating media messages. The primary focus of this literacy is on the interpretative skills required to comprehend a range of media types, including news, advertisements, social media, and entertainment. Media literacy improves a person's ability to identify persuasive techniques, spot biases, and understand the effects of media portrayals. This results in a more deliberate and critical engagement with media information.

Both information literacy and media literacy involve critical assessment abilities, yet they serve distinct purposes. Information literacy is mostly employed in academic and research environments. It facilitates the collection, evaluation, and combination of information in

order to generate new ideas or solve issues. For example, a researcher may utilize information literacy to study literature, determine the reliability of sources, and draw evidence-based conclusions. Media literacy, on the other hand, focuses on both consuming and generating media. It helps us comprehend how the

media influences our views and public opinion. It also teaches us how to develop effective media while adhering to ethical rules. The capacity to navigate information and media is critical in today's culture. Individuals who acquire talents in both areas are better prepared to understand and interact with the world around them.

Digital Literacy (DL);

Since Gilster (1997) popularized the term many decades ago, digital literacy has expanded dramatically in both breadth and application (Smith et al., 2018, 2020). Even Gilster's first definition emphasized the importance of implementing a concept of literacy in digital contexts beyond a mere aptitude for technology, emphasizing the need for literacy that involved "mastering ideas, not keystrokes" (1997, p. 15).

Martin (2006) explains that digital competence is the essential step (or level of involvement) of digital literacy, hence digital competencies and digital literacies are inextricably linked. As a result, digital literacy is frequently framed as the foundation for digital competence (Martin & Grudziecki, 2006; Spante et al., 2018).

Undergraduate students are vital in helping people build their digital literacy and information literacy skills.

These kids frequently take part in a range of activities designed to enhance their digital skills. They offer seminars, online courses, and training courses to help their colleagues use digital technologies, evaluate information critically, and become educated content producers and users in the digital age. By doing this, they ensure that their peers are not just tech-savvy but also able to think critically and communicate effectively in digital settings, bridging the gap between digital competence and digital literacy.

Libraries are essential for the advancement of digital literacy because they offer workshops and other resources to help patrons gain the digital skills they need. These abilities include using the internet, basic computer usage, and more sophisticated proficiencies like creating digital content and critically analyzing information found online. Libraries help individuals evaluate online content critically

and use digital tools effectively through workshops, classes, and one-on-one assistance. This is particularly important now that incorrect information and digital divisions are widespread. For example, Hernon and Schwartz (2016) state that libraries have played a key role in providing digital literacy programmers that encourage community empowerment and education.

People need to be digitally literate—that is, able to use digital technology effectively and critically—in order to thrive in an AI-driven future. It encompasses a range of skills, including the ability to evaluate information, utilize digital tools, and recognize the ethical implications of digital interactions (Eshet-Alkalai, 2004). Technical proficiency is only one aspect of digital literacy; other components include ethical awareness, critical thinking, and the ability to produce and convey knowledge in digital environments. According to Ng (2012), digital literacy is a multifaceted competency that encompasses the cognitive and socioemotional abilities necessary to safely traverse the digital environment in addition to the functional skills needed to operate digital tools.

Furthermore, the spread of digital tools and the quick development of technology demand constant learning and adaptability. Ferrucci et al. (2020) highlight that digital literacy is a continuous process of learning and adaptation rather than a fixed set of abilities due to the dynamic nature of digital technologies. In an increasingly automated and digital world, people need to be able to adapt and be competitive. This dynamic component of digital literacy is essential.

To succeed in an AI-driven future, kids must possess digital literacy, which is the capacity to interact with digital technology efficiently and analytically. It includes a variety of abilities, such as the capacity to assess data, use digital technologies, and comprehend the moral impacts of digital interactions. (Eshet-Alkalai, 2004) Because of this, digital literacy encompasses more than just technical ability.

The purpose of this study;

The purpose of this study is to evaluate University of Balochistan undergraduate students' knowledge, comprehension, and attitudes regarding artificial intelligence. It also aims to assess their level of digital literacy and look at the relationship between that level of proficiency and their opinions on AI. The study intends to offer practical recommendations for curriculum development that can better prepare students for the possibilities and challenges posed by AI and digital

technologies by analyzing the strengths and weaknesses in digital literacy.

Our work contributes to the growing body of research emphasizing the importance of digital literacy in the context of artificial intelligence. It emphasizes the need for educational institutions to provide students with the critical and ethical skills needed to manage the problems of an artificial

intelligence-driven world and the technical skills required for success. The study's findings will help educators, decision-makers, and other stakeholders create methods to promote digital literacy and foster current positive student views toward AI.

Research Questions;

To analysis the perceptions of Information Literacy & Digital Literacy abilities among the undergraduate students University of Balochistan.

To enquire the perceptions of Artificial Intelligence (AI) & Usage of AI in academic activities among undergraduate students University of Balochistan.

Significance of the study;

The study aimed to analyze the perception of information literacy, digital literacy, and usage of artificial intelligence in academic activities among undergraduate students, the University of Balochistan, Quetta.

Research Limitations;

The population of the study was limited to the undergraduate students of the University of Balochistan, Quetta, and the rest students were not part of the study.

Literature Review

Artificial intelligence (AI) and digital literacy abilities (DL) are becoming increasingly crucial in today's digital age, influencing many elements of society, education, and the workforce. Understanding undergraduate students' perceptions of AI and their degree of digital literacy is critical for developing successful educational interventions and preparing them for future labor market demands, (Ashok et.al, 2022).

Recent studies have focused on undergraduate students' perceptions of artificial intelligence. According to research, pupils frequently perceive AI as a strong technology with both good and bad aspects. While some see AI as a catalyst for innovation and efficiency, others are concerned about job displacement, privacy difficulties, and ethical implications, (Ashok et.al, 2022).

Salas-Pilco & Yang, (2022) expressed that Digital literacy abilities, which include the capacity to utilize digital devices, critically analyze online material, and communicate digitally, are vital for pupils in the digital age. Research has underlined the necessity of incorporating digital literacy into school curriculum to prepare students for academic performance and eventual professional preparedness. "Previous research has emphasized the need for educational institutions to prioritize AI literacy and digital skill development to guarantee that students are ready for the changing technology world. Understanding students' attitudes and skills in these areas allows educators to create interventions to improve their AI literacy and digital competence, eventually allowing them to prosper in a technology-driven environment", (Mehrabi et al., 2022).

Prioritizing AI literacy and digital skill development is crucial for educational institutions if they want to prepare their students for the rapidly changing technology landscape, according to earlier study. Teachers can design interventions to enhance students' AI literacy and digital competence and ultimately prepare them to succeed in a technology-driven environment by having a thorough understanding of the attitudes and abilities of their students in these areas (Mehrabi et al., 2022). Providing students with practical experience with digital technologies, encouraging critical thinking about the implications of technology on society, and integrating AI principles into a variety of academic subjects are examples of effective teaching tactics.

Smith et al., (2020) argue that while social media in particular and digital technologies in general have grown nearly limitless nowadays, it is problematic to confuse their prevalence with their successful use. We see students' effective use of digital technologies as requiring competencies that integrate procedural and technical, cognitive, and sociocultural abilities that are applied in different contexts, even though there are many definitions of what constitutes digital literacy. These definitions are covered in greater detail below. As Cohen and Hewitt (2019) described, "It's a common misconception that students who have grown up with technology are adept at utilizing it in a variety of settings and situations, including college courses" (para.4), highlighting the fact that, despite research indicating that most teachers think their pupils are technologically literate, students themselves seem uneasy using these resources for learning and in various academic contexts. Through continuing education and

professional development initiatives, there is a chance to reject such myths while also supporting faculty educators' own digital competencies and literacies. In these endeavors, incorporating evidence-based understandings of students' needs, abilities, and skills is crucial.

Perceptions of students as digital natives frequently increase inaccurate assumptions about their basic skills and abilities., a phrase coined by Prensky (2001) to characterize a generation of students who have grown up surrounded by technology and are therefore thought to be inherently skilled users. Although educational technology literature has thoroughly rejected simple constructions of digital natives, such hypotheses and stereotypes remain extremely common in today's culture., despite plenty of evidence to the opposed (Smith et al., 2020).

According to a recent study by Araújo-Vila et al. (2020), students frequently lack the skills necessary to successfully use digital technologies in their learning and struggle to apply the skills they do have at the required level. For this reason, it is critical to implement curriculum initiatives that explicitly develop these literacies. Through a deeper comprehension of students' views and experiences with social media technologies and associated literacies, particularly those that are most important to their undergraduate education. We may identify areas that require filling in the gaps and strengthen educational methods to address these requirements.

Methodology

This chapter addresses the methodology used to investigate the perception of information literacy, digital literacy, and usage of artificial intelligence in academic activities among undergraduate students, the University of Balochistan, Quetta.

Design of the study;

Keeping in view requirements of time according to fulfill the objectives of this study was to explore the perception of information literacy, digital literacy, and usage of artificial intelligence in academic activities among undergraduate students, the University of Balochistan, Quetta. Data were collected through structured questionnaire.

Description of the population and sample;

The sample size of this study was 300 students and only 230 respondents were given their views through Likert scale and close-ended questionnaire.

Arrangements;

The paper based questionnaire was adopted according to the objectives of the study and the research tool consisted on 14 questions, in four sections 10 were Likert scale and 04 were close- ended questions. The data were collected through online form and face to face conversations.

Validity and Reliability;

The researchers and one professional research expert was consulted for the sake of the validity of the research instrument. The research experts evaluated the tool and suggested positive change and improvements in the questionnaire. For its reliability and validity, the views of all researchers were also included in the questionnaire.

Results

In this chapter the collected data is discussed after the analysis through basic statistical methods. This chapter consisted of data interpretation and discussion; however, collected data were analyzed in Ms. Excel to draw figures, percentages, and tables to meet the objectives of the study.

Demographic information;

The demographic information of our research participants provides an exposure alpha of the

Data Collection;

The data collection was started in May,2024 and completed in May,2024 in just one month. The researchers conducted the target population personally collected the data from the targeted sample of 250 students after their positive consent.

Data analysis and interpretation;

After the data collection process, the collected data was analyzed and interpreted using Microsoft Word and Microsoft Excel to draw tables or figures, and percentages to meet the study goals.

characteristics of our sample. Where questionnaire was distributed personally by the researchers among 250 undergraduate students, and the data was collected from the respondents with a response rate of (n-250, 100%).

Frequencies across the gender; The gender distribution of our 250 respondents as follows, this indicates that 175 of the respondents were male, while 75 were female.

Figure 1. Frequency of Male and Female Students.

General perception of Artificial Intelligence (AI);

The respondents' level of familiarity with AI varied significantly. Out of the 250 participants, 22%(55 individuals) claimed to have no familiarity with AI, while 35% (8 individuals) stated that they had some familiarity. On the other hand, 43% (108 individuals) reported being very familiar with AI. This breakdown highlights the diverse range of

awareness levels among the respondents, with a slightly higher proportion having some familiarity, as shown in the figure.

Figure 2. General Perception of AI

AI technology will significantly impact the society; The graph shows a strong consensus among respondents that AI technology will significantly impact society, with a majority of 106 respondents

strongly in favor. Additionally, a significant number of 36 respondents agreed, while 60 respondents maintained a neutral stance. Conversely, 20 respondents disagreed, and 8 respondents strongly disagreed.

Figure 3. AI technology will significantly impact the society

Perceive the current integration of AI technology in education

The perceptions of respondents regarding the integration of AI technology in education presented a varied outlook. Nearly half (49%) of the respondents perceived the integration as "advanced and effective", whereas a quarter (26%) believed it

was "adequate but could be enhanced." A notable portion (21%) regarded the integration as "limited and underutilized," with a small minority (3%) expressing uncertainty about the current status of AI integration in education. Shown below

Figure 4. Perceive the current integration of AI technology in education

Not Sure 3%
 Limited & Underutilized 21%
 Adequate but could be improved 26%
 Advanced & Effective 49%

	Advanced & Effective	Adequate but could be improved	Limited & Underutilized	Not Sure
Series 1	49%	26%	21%	3%

How do you think students perceive the use of AI in their education?

When questioned about how they perceive the use of AI in their education, 56% of students

responded that they are excited and supportive. In contrast, 22% of students expressed concerns or apprehension, and another 22% remained neutral, showing a mixed bag of opinions on the use of AI in education, as shown.

Figure 5. Students perceive the use of AI in their education.

Concerned or apprehensive 22 %
 Neutral 22%
 Excited and supportive 56%
 Excited and supportive
 Neutral Concerned or apprehensive

How can AI technologies enhance the teaching-learning process in educational institutions?

Here, respondents saw AI technology enhancing education by: providing personalized learning experiences 42%, increasing student engagement 26%, automating grading and feedback 17%, and creating adaptive learning platforms 15%. Reported.

Increasing Engagement
 Personal Experience

Learning Platforms Automating Grading & Feedback
 Figure 6. How AI technology enhance teaching-learning process in education.

Perceive the current integration of AI technologies in education

Figure 9. Perceive the current integration of AI technologies in education.

Answering this question, the respondents perceived the current integration of AI technology in education as adding potential for widespread adoption across educational institutions 120%, integration into various aspect of teaching and learning 50%, development of new AI travel tools and platforms 40%, and potential for transformation change in educational practices 20%. And here is a graph to visualize the responses.

Have you received formal instruction or training in digital literacy skills as part of your education?

According to the survey, when questioned about whether they had received formal education in digital literacy skills, it was found that 18% of the participants had experienced comprehensive

training, 44% had received some training, while the majority of 38% had not received any training at all. This indicates that a considerable number of respondents might have had to acquire their digital literacy skills through alternative methods.

Figure 10. Have you received formal instruction or training in digital literacy skills

How would you rate your current level of digital literacy skills?

Answering the question to rate their current level of digital literacy. 20% of respondents consider themselves advanced, 30% intermediate, and 40% beginners; the remaining 10% are unsure about their level of digital literacy.

- Beginner
- Not Sure
- Advanced
- Intermediate

Figure 11. your current level of digital literacy skills

What challenges, if any, have you encountered in developing your digital literacy skills within the educational context?

Answering the question about the challenges they faced in developing their digital literacy skills in an educational context, respondents reported various obstacles. The top challenges included: 70% insufficient training and support from educators;

80% lack of clarity on digital literacy expectations; 30% limited access to technology or resources; and 50% difficulty keeping up with rapidly evolving technology. These findings highlight the need for educators and institutions to provide adequate support, resources, and clear guidance to help individuals develop their digital literacy skills. The graph visualizes the responses.

Figure 12. Challenges in digital literacy skills within the educational context

- Limited access to technology or resources
- Insufficient training or support from educators
- Lack of clarity on digital literacy expectations
- Difficulty in keeping up with rapidly evolving technologies

How do you think AI could be effectively integrated into educational settings to support learning and teaching?

Here the majority of respondents 65% reported being very familiar with the concept while 32% were somewhat familiar and small minority 3% were not

familiar at all this suggests that most respondents have a good understanding of how AI can effectively integrated in education learning and teaching experiences, pause also shown in the figure below.

Figure 13. AI integrated into educational settings to support learning and teaching

Have you personally experienced the use of AI technologies in your education?

According to the survey findings, it is advisable for educational establishments to enhance the utilization of AI technologies in the field of education. The results indicate that a mere 20% of participants have encountered substantial

implementation of AI in their educational journey, whereas 40% have not encountered it at all. This implies a noteworthy potential for expansion and integration of AI within educational environments, aiming to enrich the overall learning and teaching experiences.

Figure 14. Have you personally experienced the use of AI technologies in your education?

Recommendations

It is critical for educational institutions to prioritize digital literacy abilities and include formal instruction or training in these areas as part of the curriculum. The survey found that a sizable proportion of respondents had received no formal training in digital literacy abilities. This means that students should be equipped with the knowledge and abilities they need to efficiently navigate the digital world, critically assess material available online, and utilize digital tools ethically and responsibly. By incorporating digital literacy into the curriculum, educational institutions may guarantee that students are well-prepared for the challenges and possibilities that AI and future technologies provide.

There is a need to improve the integration of AI technology in educational environments to facilitate learning and teaching. According to the survey, respondents believe that the current integration of AI technology in education has the potential for widespread adoption throughout educational institutions. However, there is still potential for growth in terms of incorporating AI technology into many elements of teaching and learning, creating new AI-powered educational tools and platforms,

and effecting radical change in educational practices. By efficiently incorporating AI technology, educational institutions may improve the teaching-learning process, personalize learning experiences, and boost student engagement.

It is essential to address the problems that students confront when developing their digital literacy abilities in the school setting. The survey revealed many problems, including insufficient educator training and support, a lack of clarity on digital literacy standards, restricted access to technology or resources, and difficulty keeping up with fast changing technologies. To address these problems, educational institutions must offer proper training and support for both students and instructors, define digital literacy requirements, and provide access to technology and resources.

Furthermore, continual efforts should be made to stay up with technological changes and improve digital literacy programs as needed. Overall, by prioritizing digital literacy skills, improving AI technology integration, and addressing student challenges, educational institutions can better prepare students for the digital age and

provide them with the skills and knowledge they need to thrive in an AI-driven world. These guidelines can help to build successful educational interventions that improve students' digital literacy skills, as well as their knowledge and use of AI technology.

Conclusion;

This study on undergraduate students' perceptions of AI and digital literacy abilities at the University of Balochistan sheds light on educational requirements and preparedness for the digital age. The study's findings emphasize the relevance of AI integration in educational settings, as well as the requirement for digital literacy skills to prosper in today's society. By addressing these issues through focused interventions and curricular revisions, educational institutions may better prepare students to negotiate the complexities of AI technology and thrive in a digitally connected world.

It is clear that students' perceptions of AI and digital literacy abilities may be improved by effectively integrating AI technology into school, developing digital literacy skills, and continuously improving educational methods. By following the suggestions above mentioned, the University of Balochistan can guarantee that its students have the requisite skills and knowledge to tackle the challenges and possibilities given by AI and digital technologies. This will help not just the pupils, but also the society as a whole.

As a whole, this study emphasizes the necessity for educational institutions to adapt and change in response to the rapid progress of artificial intelligence and digital technology. By focusing on AI integration and digital literacy, the University of Balochistan can help students prepare for the digital age and succeed in a technology-driven environment.

REFERENCES

- Ashok, M., Madan, R., Joha, A., & Sivarajah, U. (2022). Ethical framework for Artificial Intelligence and Digital technologies. *International Journal of Information Management*, 62, 102433. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2021.102433>
- Mehrabi, N., Morstatter, F., Saxena, N., Lerman, K., & Galstyan, A. (2022). A Survey on Bias and Fairness in Machine Learning. *ACM Computing Surveys*, 54(6), 1-35. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3457607>
- Salas-Pilco, S. Z., & Yang, Y. (2022). Artificial intelligence applications in Latin American higher education: a systematic review. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 19(1), 21. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-022-00326-w>
- Eshet-Alkalai. (2004). Digital literacy: A conceptual framework for survival skills in the digital era. *Digital literacy: A conceptual framework for survival skills in the digital era. Journal of Educational Multimedia and Hypermedia*.
- Peter Norvig, s. r. (2020). *Artificial Intelligence: A Modern Approach*. New Jersey : Pearson Education.
- Eshet, Y. (2004). Digital literacy: A conceptual framework for survival skills in the digital era. *Journal of Educational Multimedia and Hypermedia*, 13(1), 93-106.
- Russell, S., & Norvig, P. (2020). *Artificial Intelligence: A Modern Approach* (4th ed.). Pearson.
- Smith, A., & Anderson, J. (2018). AI, Robotics, and the Future of Jobs. Pew Research Center. Retrieved from <https://www.pewresearch.org/internet/2018/05/03/ai-robotics-and-the-future-of-jobs/>.
- Irizarry-Nones, A., Palepu, A., & Wallace, M. (2017). Artificial intelligence (AI). Retrieved from: www.bu.edu/lernet/artemis/years/2017/projects/FinalPresentations/A.I.%20Presentation.pdf
- Cohen, J., & Hewitt, R. (2019, April 23). When bringing your own device isn't enough

- Identifying what digital literacy initiatives really need. EDUCAUSE Review. HTTPs
<https://er.educause.edu/blogs/2019/4/when-bringing-your-own-device-isnt-enough-identifying-what-digital-literacy-initiatives-really-need>
- Prensky, M. (2001). Digital natives, digital immigrants part 1. On the Horizon, 9(5), 1-6.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/10748120110424816>
- Sharun, S., & Smith, E. E. (2020). Educational development partnerships and practices: Helping librarians move beyond the one-shot. College & Research Libraries News, 81(9), 445-449.
<https://doi.org/10.5860/crln.81.9.445>
- Araújo-Vila, N., Cardoso, L., Toubes, D. R., & Fraiz-Brea, J. A. (2020). Digital competence in Spanish university education and its use by students. Publications, 8(4), 47.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/publications8040047>
- UNICEF. (2019). Digital literacy for children— 10 things to know.
<https://www.unicef.org/globalinsight/documents/digital-literacy-children-10-things-know>
- Rosen, D. J., & Stewart, C. (2015). Blended learning/or the adult education classroom. Essential Education. Retrieved from <http://app.essential.ed.com/resources/blended-learning-teachers-guide-web.pdf>
- Siemens, G. (2004). Connectivism: A learning theory for the digital age. Retrieved from http://www.itdl.org/Journal/Jan_05/article01.htm
- Vanek, J. (2017). Using the PIAAC framework for problem solving in technology-rich environments to guide instruction: An introduction for adult educators. Retrieved from https://static1.squarespace.com/static/51bb74b8e4b0139570ddf020/t/589a3d3c1e5b6cd7b42cddb/1486503229769/PSTRE_Guide_Vanek_2017.pdf
- Vanek, J. (in press). Second language proficiency, academic language, and digital literacy for LESLLA learners. Proceedings from the Second Language Acquisition Symposium. Portland, OR: Portland State University.
- Vanek, J., Simpson, D., Johnston, J., & Petty, L. I. (2018, August). IDEAL distance education and blended learning handbook (6th ed.). Boston, MA: World Education. Retrieved from <https://edtech.world.ed.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/IDEAL-Handbook-6th-Edition-8-16-18.pdf>
- Wyatt, M. (2018). Why it is important to be digitally literate in the 21st century. Retrieved from <https://medium.com/literate-schools/why-it-is-important-to-be-digitally-literate-in-the-21st-century-583000ac8fc0>
- U.S. Department of Education, Office of Vocational and Adult Education. (2013). College and career readiness standards for adult education. Washington, D.C.: Author. Retrieved from https://lincs.ed.gov/publications/pdf/CCRStandard_sAdultEd.pdf

